

Diagnostic Value of Capillary Density at Periungual Capillaroscopy in the Diagnosis of Connective Tissue Disease

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Abstract

Our study aims to demonstrate the contribution of quantitative analysis of capillaroscopic study in the early diagnosis of connective tissue diseases. One hundred and fifteen patients were evaluated by capillaroscopy. Raynaud's phenomenon is the most frequently encountered acro-syndrome leading to the request for capillaroscopic examination. capillaroscopy reveals minor dystrophy in 83.5% of patients and major dystrophy in 60% of them. On a quantitative level, 77 patients present, among the four examined fingers, at least one finger with a capillary density <25 capillaries/3mm. For the diagnosis of connective tissue disease, this threshold is statistically significant with an odds ratio of 4.21 (95% CI = 1.47-11.99; p = 0.008). For this same diagnosis, its positive predictive value is 38%, its negative predictive value is 86%. A low capillary density, as a diagnostic test for connective tissue disease, has a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 41%. There is no significant difference between the decrease in capillary density for the diagnosis of connective tissue disease for each examined finger in terms of positive predictive value, negative predictive value, sensitivity, and specificity

Introduction

Capillaroscopy is a non-invasive, reproducible examination useful in the etiological diagnosis of an acro-syndrome [1-5]. It is particularly decisive in the early diagnosis of systemic sclerosis (pre-scleroderma states) and in its evaluation [6]. Capillary pathology is

not exclusive to scleroderma. It is associated with numerous endocrine, neurological, and cardiovascular pathologies. However, it is specifically linked, in addition to scleroderma, to rheumatic and autoimmune diseases such as inflammatory myopathy, antiphospholipid syndrome, systemic lupus

More Information

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erythematosus, and Sjögren's syndrome [7]. In scleroderma, it has been demonstrated that the severity of capillaropathy observed in capillaroscopy reflects histological and functional impairments [8]. This microvascular involvement is correlated with organ involvement, notably pulmonary, renal, and cardiac [9]. Capillaroscopic study is multifaceted. Various qualitative, semi-quantitative, and quantitative methods are employed. Architectural analysis of capillaries, their distribution, and morphological aspects define qualitative study. Analysis of capillary bed abnormalities (capillary dilatation, branching, tortuosity, mega-capillary) corresponds to semi-quantitative study. Quantitative study is performed through analysis of capillary density. Our study aims to demonstrate the contribution of quantitative analysis in the early diagnosis of connective tissue diseases.

Materials and Methods

In our study, we have used a capillaroscopy device capable of performing video-capillaroscopy with image storage and measurement of capillary diameters. It features epi-illumination with cold light oriented at a 45-degree angle relative to the periungual edge. The device is manufactured by Leika. Capillaries appear horizontal with respect to the skin plane. After the application of a drop of immersion microscope oil to eliminate artifacts, magnification between 20 and 200 times can be achieved, enhancing image sharpness. Capillaroscopy is conducted in a room at ambient temperature: 20-22°C.

The capillary density of patients is systematically studied on four fingers: the ring and middle fingers of each hand. The finger position analyzed is orthogonal

to the objective. Capillaries are visually counted over a 3mm field. Low capillary density is defined by the presence, on at least one finger, of a number fewer than 25 capillaries per 3mm. Positive and negative predictive values, sensitivity, and specificity are assessed for connective tissue diseases in patients presenting with an acro-syndrome.

One hundred and fifteen consecutive patients undergoing capillaroscopy are included. The inclusion criterion is the presence of an acro-syndrome defined by the presence of permanent or paroxysmal vasomotor disturbances: primary and secondary Raynaud's phenomenon, erythromelalgia, chilblains, acrodermatitis, and acro-osteolysis. Patients with extremity amputation or those in whom obtaining an analyzable image is difficult are excluded. EpiDATA and EpiInfo software were used for statistical analysis.

Results

One hundred and fifteen patients were evaluated by capillaroscopy. The clinical and demographic characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The population in our series is young, with a mean age of 38.2 years and predominantly female. Raynaud's phenomenon is the most frequently encountered acro-syndrome leading to the request for capillaroscopic examination, accounting for 87.8%. In our series, 30.4% of patients have a connective tissue disease, including systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic sclerosis, and mixed connective tissue disease.

On the qualitative level, as shown in Table 2, capillaroscopy reveals minor dystrophy in 83.5% of patients and major dystrophy in 60% of them.

Table 1: Patients Clinical Characteristics

Patients clinical characteristics	
Age (year ±SD)	38,2 ± 14
Female (%)	84,3
Acro-syndrome (%)	87,8
Raynaud (%)	71,3
Bilateral (%)	81,7
Symmetric (%)	69,6
Trophic disorders	13,0
Ulceration (%)	6,0
Calcinosis (%)	1,7
Necrosis (%)	2,6
Pulp scar (%)	9,6
Systemic pathology	30,4
Systemic lupus erythematosus (%)	13,0
Systemic sclerosis (%)	11,3
Mixed connective tissue disease (%)	7,8
Rheumatoid arthritis (%)	1,0
Vasculitis (%)	7,0
Treatment	
Calcium channel blockers	84,3

Hydroxychloroquine	73,9
Corticosteroids	80,0
Immunosuppressants	91,2

Table 2: Patients Capillaroscopic Data

Patients Capillaroscopic data	
Minor dystrophies	83,5 (moy 4,59±2,87)
Slot	30,4
Caduceus	31,1
Dilated capillaries	57,4
Loop	40,0
Tortuous	43,5
Major dystrophies	60 (moy2,6±2,99)
Mega-capillary	27,5
Branching	31,3
Corkscrew	16,3
Microaneurysm	17,5
Thrombosed capillaries	23,8
Fishbone pattern	8,8
Organic hemorrhage	60
Avascular patches	17,5
Capillary disorganization	23,8

On a quantitative level, 77 patients present, among the four examined fingers (3rd and 4th fingers on both right and left hands), at least one finger with a capillary density <25 capillaries/3mm. For the diagnosis of connective tissue disease, this threshold is statistically significant with an odds ratio of 4.21 (95% CI = 1.47-11.99; p = 0.008). For this same diagnosis, its positive predictive value is 38%, its negative predictive value is

86%. A low capillary density, as a diagnostic test for connective tissue disease, has a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 41%. As demonstrated in Table 3 comparing the decrease in capillary density for the diagnosis of connective tissue disease for each examined finger, there is no significant difference between them in terms of positive predictive value, negative predictive value, sensitivity, and specificity.

Table 3: Low Capillary Density (less than 25/3mm) in Each Finger as a Diagnostic Test for Connective Tissue Diseases

	III Right	IV Right	III Left	IV Left
Positive Predictive Value	46	36	43	46
Negative Predictive value	84	75	82	81
Sensitivity	74	60	71	65
Specificity	62	53	58	66

Discussion

The lack of recommendations from scientific societies regarding the modalities and interpretation of capillaroscopic examination represents one of the main drawbacks for its relevant exploitation and rational use [10]. Capillaroscopic examination in connective tissue diseases highlights various major dystrophies such as disorganization of the capillary bed, major dystrophies characterized by mega-capillaries, branched capillaries, and reduced capillary density. Currently, there is no standardization in the diagnostic approach to capillaroscopic images and medical report writing [11]. Several authors advocate for evaluation (qualitative, semi-quantitative, quantitative), and various methods of quantifying capillary abnormalities include

measuring the number of loops in the distal row over 5 mm. The reduction in the number of capillaries can predict the appearance of avascular areas in patients with Raynaud's phenomenon and can signify severity, necessitating monitoring through iterative capillaroscopies [12]. For clinicians, this could mean better control of the underlying condition (e.g., cessation of certain therapies such as beta-blockers and ergot derivatives, introduction of vasodilators, etc.). The discovery of major dystrophies (mega-capillaries, disorganization, capillary rarefaction, branched capillaries) can provide clinicians with the opportunity to detect an undiagnosed connective tissue disease and differentiate Raynaud's diseases from Raynaud's syndrome. In a study of 74 patients explored for

Raynaud's phenomenon, two parameters significantly associated with the development of connective tissue disease were periungual capillary abnormalities and altered pulmonary function tests. In 639 patients with Raynaud's phenomenon, the best predictive value for connective tissue disease is the presence of capillaroscopic anomalies, which has a positive predictive value of 47%. Additionally, the association of capillary abnormalities with sausage fingers is an independent predictive factor in the development of systemic sclerosis. Furthermore, patients who experience loss of the capillary bed have a more severe disease course compared to those with preserved capillary beds. Severe microvascular involvement in systemic sclerosis is strongly associated with reduced capillary density. Concurrently, our study aims to optimize capillary bed examination time, particularly in calculating capillary density over 3 mm and in all four fingers (ring and middle fingers) of each hand, with a threshold value of 25 capillaries/field. The reduction in the number is correlated with underlying connective tissue disease, with sensitivity and specificity of 85% and 41%, respectively, along with a good negative predictive value of 86% and a positive predictive value of 38% ($p = 0.008$). This underscores the necessity of standardizing capillaroscopic examination to facilitate a better approach in the early diagnosis of connective tissue diseases in cases of Raynaud's phenomenon, and especially to identify patients at risk of developing severe microvascular involvement in their disease.

Conclusion

Capillaroscopy represents a very valuable means of etiological and prognostic diagnosis, particularly in the early diagnosis and evaluation of connective tissue diseases [13]. It allows for the identification of a high-risk group of patients for ischemic necrosis due to severe microvascular involvement. The calculation of capillary density appears to have an interesting negative predictive value in this evaluation for connective tissue diseases, despite the lack of standardization of the examination [14, 15]. However, many controversies on this subject necessitate further research to validate these observations.

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